

Tourist Movement Patterns as an Evaluation Indicator for Mandalika-Mataram Tourism Planning

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Abstract

Visitor movement patterns provide an important basis for spatial and transportation planning considerations because they reflect how planned infrastructure operates in real life. Using tourist movement patterns in the Mandalika-Mataram corridor, West Nusa Tenggara Province, Indonesia, as an indicator for channeling tourism planning, this study aims to conduct this analysis. The study focuses on three main movement hubs: Mataram City as a service and transit hub, Lombok International Airport as the main entry point, and Mandalika, a tourist area, as the primary destination. A node-link model based on secondary geospatial data, such as road networks, administrative boundaries, and the distribution of tourist destinations, was used in a spatial analytic technique. The concentration of tourist movements between nodes, movement direction, and network structure were all examined using Geographic Information System (GIS) technologies. The findings indicate that the Mandalika tourist region, the airport, and Mataram City are connected by a linear north-south structure of tourist movement patterns. While ancillary road networks have a smaller importance, tourist movements are mostly centered along the major corridor connecting these nodes. This trend suggests that real tourist mobility and the planned spatial arrangement are closely related. The study comes to the conclusion that visitor mobility patterns can be a useful metric for assessing how well tourism spatial design is working. The concentration along a single corridor emphasizes the necessity of strengthening supporting networks to promote spatial connectedness, even though the current planning effectively directs movement toward important tourist attractions.

Keywords: Visitor movement patterns; spatial planning; node-link analysis

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Introduction

Movement is an important component of regional planning because it reflects how people interact with existing space and resources (Sasmitasari, Reza, and Nurul 2023). In the field of tourism, tourist movement not only shows the direction and level of visiting activity, but also illustrates the extent to which the transportation network is able to support accessibility to tourist destinations, which is important in regional planning because it reflects the way humans interact with existing space and resources (Raharjo and Fitasari 2023). The relationship between road systems and tourism activities is increasingly significant to understand, because tourist movement patterns can indicate how well regional planning has met the needs of the tourism sector (Sofi and Susilowati 2017). Tourism is one of the main sectors that drives regional development, both through improving the local economy and spreading social and cultural benefits (Huda 2020). In this context, road infrastructure plays an important role in determining the comfort of tourists when accessing various destinations (Hartini 2025). Bypass roads, as part of transportation planning efforts, not only reduce travel distances but also help direct tourist movements in line with regional development strategies (Kurniawan and Qodir 2022). Therefore, analyzing how roads, particularly bypass roads, are used by tourists can provide empirical evidence of the effectiveness of tourism planning in a region.

The Mandalika area has been designated a Super Priority Tourism Destination (DPSP) with a national strategic position (Zitri et al. 2024). Access to this area relies heavily on Lombok International Airport (BIL) as the main entry point for tourists, while Mataram City serves as a hub for economic, social, and hospitality services. The two locations are connected by the Airport-Mandalika Bypass Road, designed to improve connectivity and facilitate tourist mobility to core tourism areas. With this spatial structure, tourist movement patterns between Mataram, the airport, and Mandalika serve as an important indicator in assessing the extent to which the transportation network effectively supports the integration of tourism areas (Sutiarso 2018).

However, although the road network in this region offers several routes to other tourist destinations in southern Lombok, tourist movement tends to remain concentrated along the main bypass corridor. This phenomenon raises two possibilities: either this pattern demonstrates successful planning that directs tourist movement along strategic routes, or it reflects an over reliance on a single route, hindering the delivery of economic benefits to the surrounding area. To answer this question, a spatial analysis that evaluates actual tourist movement patterns is needed as a basis for planning assessment (Habir and Loeis 2020).

Previous research usually focuses on aspects of physical infrastructure and transportation systems in the context of developing the Mandalika area (Maulana et al. 2023). Despite contributing to understanding the role of road networks, most studies have not considered tourist movement patterns as a primary indicator for evaluating the effectiveness of tourism planning. However, analyzing tourist movement patterns can provide more dynamic empirical data by demonstrating tourists' actual behavior in relation to the designed spatial system. This limitation presents a gap that needs to be addressed through further research.

This study aims to analyze tourist movement patterns as an indicator for evaluating tourism planning in the Mandalika-Mataram region. Scientifically, this research contributes to enriching

regional planning studies based on spatial data and tourist behavior. Practically, the research findings are expected to serve as a basis for local governments and destination managers in designing transportation and spatial planning policies to ensure synergistic and sustainable road network systems and tourism activities.

Introduction consists of (in sequence) general background, state of the art as the basis for the scientific novelty statement of the article, scientific novelty statement, and research problem or hypothesis. At the end, the introduction should mention the purpose of the article review. Literature review is not allowed in the scientific article format, so it is replaced by the state of the art to prove the novelty of the article.

Research Methods

The Mandalika-Mataram Corridor, located in West Nusa Tenggara Province, comprises three main points of tourist movement: Mataram City as a service and transit hub, Lombok International Airport as the main entry point, and the Mandalika area as a major tourist destination. A network of bypass roads and other supporting roads forms the regional movement system. This study uses secondary spatial data in the form of road networks, administrative boundaries, and the distribution of tourist destinations obtained from geospatial sources and official planning documents. The data was processed and analyzed using a Geographic Information System (GIS). In this analysis, a node-link model is used to examine tourist movement patterns between nodes. Nodes represent the starting point, destination, and transit points of travel, while links represent the connecting road network. Movement patterns are analyzed based on the direction and concentration of travel. The results are used as a basis for assessing the performance of spatial planning to improve tourist accessibility to the Mandalika-Mataram corridor.

Results and Discussion

Identify Node Movement Structure

The analysis shows that the three main centers of tourist movement in the study area are Mataram City, Zainuddin Abdul Madjid Airport, and the Mandalika area. Mataram City serves as a transportation and service hub, the airport serves as the main entry point for tourists, and Mandalika serves as a major tourist destination. These three nodes are spatially connected, forming a north-south oriented linear configuration that connects urban service centers, air transportation nodes, and recreational areas in the Mandalika-Mataram corridor.

Figure 1. Map Of Research Nodes
Source: Analysis Results (2025)

Network Structure and Branching

Based on the spatial analysis, the tourist transportation network structure in the study area consists of one main route connecting Mataram City, Zainuddin Abdul Madjid International Airport, and the Mandalika area. In the tourist movement system, the main route is a bypass road that serves as a direct connection between major nodes. Several supporting routes, particularly in the areas around Mataram City and Mandalika, branch off the network and serve as alternative routes to reach the main nodes. This network configuration forms a linear movement pattern with limited branching.

Figure 2. Map Of Research Linkage
Source: Analysis Results (2025)

Tourist Movement Patterns

The north-south route connecting Mataram City, Zainuddin Abdul Madjid International Airport, and the Mandalika area is the primary route for visitors. The corridors connecting these three nodes demonstrate the focus of movement, particularly on sections directly connecting the main nodes. While support routes are used around certain points, the bypass road connecting Mataram to the airport and Mandalika is the most frequently used.

Figure 3. Map Of Movement Direction
Source: Analysis Results (2025)

The results of the study indicate that the tourist movement system in the Mandalika-Mataram corridor is structured linearly, with Mataram City, Zainuddin Abdul Madjid International Airport, and the Mandalika area closely connected to each other. This pattern indicates that the planned spatial structure and transportation network have formed a relatively directed orientation of tourist movement towards key nodes with strategic functions. In the planning evaluation, this condition indicates that spatial planning has succeeded in concentrating tourist movement on the main corridor connecting service centers, entrances, and major tourist destinations. The high volume of traffic on the bypass route demonstrates that the infrastructure serves as a hub for the tourist transportation system. This route enables direct mobility between key nodes, effectively strengthening the integration of the Mandalika region with urban and regional transportation systems. From a planning perspective, this aligns with the strategic corridor development objectives, which aim to improve accessibility to key tourism areas.

However, the limited supporting paths and unbranched movement patterns indicate that visitor movement remains concentrated within a single main corridor. This indicates that the spatial structure has not fully encouraged visitor activity to areas surrounding the main corridor. The results of the planning evaluation can be interpreted as indicating that road network planning focuses more on direct connectivity than on enhancing spatial linkages between buffer zones.

Therefore, tourist movement patterns can be used as a measure of the effectiveness of spatial planning. The fact that the transportation network plan is consistent with actual movement patterns

indicates the appropriateness of the planning. However, it also suggests that building a supporting network would enable a more distributed and spatially integrated movement system.

Conclusion

This study found that the Mandalika-Mataram corridor has a linear pattern connecting Mataram City, Zainuddin Abdul Madjid International Airport, and the Mandalika area as a major transportation hub. This pattern is supported by a road network structure focused on one main corridor a bypass road that directly connects strategic nodes. The results indicate that tourist movement patterns align with the planned spatial structure and transportation network. Therefore, this movement pattern can be used as a measure to assess the performance of tourism planning. However, the concentration of movement in one corridor also indicates an opportunity to build a supporting network to improve spatial connectivity more evenly in the surrounding environment.

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